

BJP Visions on Equality and Inequality Rights of the Women a Review

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: October

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Vasanthakumar, V. "BJP Visions on Equality and Inequality Rights of the Women a Review." *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 216–19.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3549316>

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There Are distinct Various stages of rise and fall in the status of the women in our Indian context. It is stated in the Vedic period that women participation in all the fields like men.that took active part in every sphere of the human life. Women are man's friend, co-worker and never inferior to him theyenjoys the property rights and have access to the property of her father and husband, Women struggle against the political as well as the social problems freely with men. Women go to the Guru Kula to receive education and getting married. During the Vedic period, women occupied the high position in our society and used to move freely society.

The Indo-Anglican novel, right since it begins. Socio-political milieu wherein it takes birth and has been written since. The national political consciousness in India was slowly percolating the grass-roots. 'Indeed this sense of commitment to the national awareness was an important factor which this paper is reviewing the present political scenario through the hands of Pre and Post independence Women writers concern like Arundati Roy,Nayantara Sahgal.

The Piece of Work is Woman

In form, in moving, and express admirable

In action how they look like an angel.

In apprehension how like a God!

at the same time it is also said.

Frailty — thy name is woman.

Changing the status involves sharing of the power on equal footing with men in decision making and in implementation at informal and formal levels. The social value framework plays an important role in determining the changing status of the power equations, and,the status of women involves in distribution and redistribution of the power. Furtherely the half of the world's population is the owner and two thirds of the working force consists of women. In India, The BJP Lok Sabha election manifesto promises, the 'Sankalpith Bharat, to ensure gender equality in our Indian society. The sensitive issues like the triple talaq and niqah halala have also found its place in the manifesto to woo the women voters towards the BJP. Senior

leaders such as Narendra Modi, Adhvani, Amit Shah, Rajnath Singh, and Sushma Swaraj took the stage to speak about the party's accomplishments in the past five years with its promises. They spoke about ensuring a life of dignity for women, women's safety, promotion of gender justice and the reservation for women. However, a close look at their party manifesto will reveal the grave Ersatz Aides in that promise. The BJP Lok Sabha has as many as 78 women have been elected to the Lok Sabha. This is the highest representation of women the Lower House has ever seen. The number is up from what was 62 in 2014. However, this 14 percent representation is significantly less than what is seen in other countries such as Bangladesh (21 percent), United States (24 percent) and United Kingdom (32 percent) Women in the Lower House.

BJP has determinedly taken substantive measures to ensure overall the development of the women to promote the gender equality by Continuing their work, BJP will legislate a bill to prohibit and eliminate practices such as the triple talaq and Nikah Halala," the manifesto reads. Women's security will be given more priority. They have constituted the Women's Security Division in the Home Ministry, and have made a strict provisions for transferring the laws in order to commit crimes against the women, particularly in a time-bound investigation and the trail for a rape. In such cases, forensic facilities and fast track courts will be expanded to bring convicts to justice.

BJP feel that the best way to show respect for women is to extend protection for them under a patriarchal system and confine them to traditional roles at home. UP, which the BJP is hoping to capture electorally, is among the worst when it comes to crimes against women. In the four years leading to 2015, violent crimes against women increased by a staggering 34% across India, with UP, Maharashtra, West Bengal and Rajasthan at the bottom of the heap.

Few political parties have taken up the issue of women's rights and violence against them. States ruled by the BJP, like Rajasthan and Haryana, have among the worst sex ratios. This is largely the result of female foeticide, a horrific form of violence against women. The figures for all crimes, including trafficking, rape, and domestic violence and stalking have gone up.

At the same time, the criminal justice system is so difficult for women to negotiate that many cases just fall by the wayside. There are strong and adequate laws to protect women but awareness is still very patchy.

In a major goof-up, the BJP manifesto reads that the party's government has made strict provisions "for transferring the laws in order to commit crimes" against women, instead of checking crimes against women under its chapter on Women Empowerment.

"We have constituted the Women's Security Division in the Home Ministry, and have made strict provisions for transferring the laws in order to commit crimes against women..." Shah's induction into the Union cabinet is such an interesting moment. Shah is a political genius. Under his leadership, the BJP has become an electoral behemoth in the most complicated political landscape in the world. 'Sankalp Bharat, to exploits

Beti Bachao Beti Padhao Scheme, One Stop Centre Scheme Women Helpline Scheme UJJAWALA: A Comprehensive Scheme for Prevention of trafficking and Rescue, Rehabilitation and Re-integration of Victims of Trafficking and Commercial Sexual Exploitation Working Women Hostel Ministry approves new projects under Ujjawala Scheme and continues existing project SWADHAR Greh (A Scheme for Women in Difficult Circumstances) Support for Training and the Employment Programme for Women (STEP) NARI SHAKTI PURASKARA wardees of Stree Shakti Puruskar, 2014 & Awardees of Nari Shakti Puruskar Awardees of Rajya Mahila Samman & Zila Mahila Samman Mahila police Volunteers Mahila E-Haat Mahila Shakti Kendras (MSK) NIRBHAYA

Health the BJP Lok Sabha election manifesto mentioned Mission Indradhanush, programme for immunization of 3.39 crore children and 87.18 lakh pregnant mothers and promising to ensure

furtherly immunization of the pregnant women by 2022.”The Mission Indradhanush programme has ensured the full immunization of 3.39 crore children and 87.18 lakh pregnant mothers. Furtherly, the annual increase in the rate of immunization has jumped from 1 percent per year to 6 percent. Continuing this article, we will ensure the full immunization coverage for all the children and pregnant women by 2022,” the manifesto includes.

Sports the BJP Lok Sabha election manifesto also promises to develop the culture of sports in our country with a special attention to encourage the participation of women. Our government has taken comprehensive steps to develop the culture of sports in the country through the ‘Khelo India’ scheme, and it will continue to provide an adequate resources under this scheme to ensure their achievement of declared objectives. Under this scheme the special attention will be given to encourage the sporting talent among the women and tribal’s as the manifesto includes

Education the BJP LookSabah election manifesto invokes the ‘Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao’ programme and they said if the party come back to power again they would continue to build on what they had achieved so far in providing the education to all women. The gain make under our pioneering ‘Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao’ programme have been an impressive. We are committed to continuing to build on these gains for providing the accessible and affordable quality of education to all the women. We will ensure that the ample financial support is available to girls throughout their education and subsidised education and loans are provided for their higher education,”as the manifesto includes.

Financial Empowerment, the BJP Lok Sabha election manifesto mentioned schemes like Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, Ujjwala, Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana, and Saubhagya and said that the government’s focus has been on ensuring a safe and dignified life for the women. This manifesto also says that if voted to the power, the government will ensure financial empowerment for the women entrepreneurs and farmers. During the last five years, we have been focussing on ensuring a safe and dignified life and the access to basic their resource for the women through various schemes such as Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, Ujjwala, Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana, Saubhagya. Few years to ensure the financial empowerment among the women in rural and semi-rural areas to create a better employment opportunities to them, we will have every effort to ensure the access to credit other resources, capacity building, market and distribution network for the women entrepreneurs such as SHGs and the women farmers,” as the manifesto includes.

Workforce the BJP Lok Sabha election manifesto says that the party is committed to making the women equal partners in the progress of the nation and it will ensure the increasing of the women workforce participation rate over the next five years. We are committed to make the women equal partners equal beneficiaries of the progress and the prosperity of the nation the will formulate a comprehensive ‘Women in Workforce’ roadmap focussed on dramatically increasing the women workforce for participating the rate over the next five years. We will also encourage the industries and corporates to generate the better employment opportunities for the women,”as the manifesto includes.

Maternal healthcare, The BJP Lok Sabha election manifesto promises to ensure a good quality and easily accessible and affordable for the maternal healthcare services for all the women for Continuing our efforts to ensure safe motherhood through schemes such as the Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana, Pradhan Mantri Matritva Suraksha Abhiyaan and Ayushman Bharat, we will focus on ensuring a good quality and easily accessible and affordable maternal healthcare services for all women as the manifesto includes.

The BJP also promises to provide a sanitary pads at an affordable cost of just Re 1. We will ensure that all the reproductive and menstrual health services are easily available to all the women in India and with the expansion of ongoing Suidha scheme, sanitary pads at an affordable cost of just Re 1 will be provided to all women and girls as the manifesto includes.

Security the BJP Lok Sabha election manifesto emphasizes on providing a security to the women on priority. We have constituted the Women's Security Division in the Home Ministry, for having made a strict provisions for transferring the laws in order to commit crimes against women, particularly in a time-bound investigation and the trail for a rape. In such cases a forensic facilities and fast track courts will be expanded to bring the convicts to justice, "as the manifesto includes.

Reservation for Women, the BJP Lok Sabha election manifesto also promises reservation for the women in the Parliament and all the state assemblies through a Constitutional amendment the Women's welfare and development will be accorded to a high priority at all levels the government, and the BJP is committed to 33% of the reservation in the Parliament and all the state assemblies through a Constitutional amendment, "as the manifesto includes.

BJP follows Gandhi's philosophy, a woman has a right to education. according to him education develops and sharpens one's intellect and it increases one's capacity for doing well.

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